

Original Research Article

Enhancement of organic carbon formation with QBLOCK™ in Pumice Sand

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Declining soil fertility continues to hinder agricultural production, especially among resource-constrained smallholder farmers. There are numerous studies on different soil functions, namely water and nutrient supply, carbon sequestration, organic matter recycling, and soil biodiversity. However, the importance of oxygen levels in soil and their significant impact on different parameters of fertility has gone unnoticed. The purpose of this work is to demonstrate the unusual importance that dissolved oxygen levels have on the fertility of agricultural soil. It can be said that if we strive to raise and maintain high oxygen levels, soil fertility tends to recover without the need for phosphates or nitrogenous compounds. The materials used include a substrate that is particularly difficult to grow: Pumice soil, with which we cover the QBLOCKS in a proportion of one gram of QBLOCK for every five (5) grams of Pumice soil. To the resulting sample, purified water was added to completely cover the surface of the mixture. The control of the experiment was mainly photographic since the methods of soil analysis to determine the degree of organic carbon are particularly polluting. The experiment started in June 2022, and the results are up to February 2023, and even though the experiment continues, we think it is important to report the results we are obtaining. During the first 4 months, nothing seems to happen, except for the formation of small spaces in the uniform surface of the Pumice soil. But the first manifestation of the appearance of organic carbon was small green spots on the surface illuminated by natural light. From then on, the formation of other zones compatible with the appearance of organic carbon evolved rapidly. Soil fertility depends mainly on the levels of oxygen it contains and not so much on nitrogen and phosphate. On the contrary, the indiscriminate use of these compounds has gradually reduced the soil's ability to naturally absorb oxygen, which is how nature has done since the beginning of time. We hope that experiments as demonstrative as this one help to correct the collective error of the use of fertilizers.

Keywords: Amorphous aluminum silicate, Oxygen, Pumice, Soil, Water.

Background

Soon, will be necessary to develop food sources for future astronauts living and operating in deep space. It is fundamental to plant growth researchers working to unlock agricultural innovations that could help us understand how plants might overcome stressful conditions in food-scarce

areas here on Earth, and eventually apply it to complex conditions like lunar surface environment.

Soils usually repelled water (were hydrophobic) causing the water to bead up on the surface. Active stirring of the soil with water can break the hydrophobicity and uniformly wet the soil, but energy expenditure for stirring is

considerable and is practical only in small samples of soil but not for greater areas of culture. Once small samples are moistened, the soils could be wetted by capillary action for plant culture.

In reported experiments to grow *Arabidopsis* in samples of soil collected on Apollo missions, besides stirring, a non-specified nutrient solution was added daily. However, the plants were not as robust as the control group, such as when soil has too much salt or heavy metals.

In Earth harsh environments, or in Lunar or Mars soil, is necessary to develop strategies to someday growing plants, because plants what enable us to be explorers.

QBLOCK™ is a new material developed in our facilities based in the human eye's biology. It has a substantive effect in dissolved oxygen levels when is immersed in water, but this increase (in oxygen levels) also occurs when it is buried in cultivable soils.

In this work we are reporting organic carbon appearance in amorphous aluminum silicate (Pumice), a light-colored, highly porous igneous rock that forms during explosive volcanic eruptions, when is placed with water in presence of QBLOCK™.

Introduction

Plants have long been envisioned as part of lunar habitats (Wheeler, 2010) and exploration environments (Wolff *et al*, 2018). The extent to which plants can enhance human life support on other worlds depends on our ability to enhancement of plants to thrive in extraterrestrial environments using in-situ resources (Barker *et al*, 2020).

While plants can be grown hydroponically, the process requires a significant amount of water, which might be in short supply. So, for missions that will land on a body like the Moon or Mars, growing plants in the local soil might be a better solution (Seedhouse and Shayler, 2019). But local soils on these bodies don't look like the ones we find on Earth, which have a complicated mix of minerals, organic compounds, and microbial life. With the main to answer the question about that plants can adjust to these differences, we choose a material coming from volcanic origin: the amorphous aluminum silicate $(Al_2O_3)_2(SiO_2)$ $[AS_2]$ or Pumice (Winkler *et al*, 2004), as a harsh substrate like lunar soil conditions.

The lunar soil exists in a form called regolith, which is basically loose, dusty material created by the constant bombardment of lunar rocks by micrometeorites. Lunar regolith containing higher amounts of titanium and some trace minerals. Earth's oxidizing environment also creates some differences in the chemical state of some of the metals present, including that of iron, a key component of many enzymes, such as those involved in photosynthesis. There are some physical differences between the material and the soil. The rapid melting and cooling caused by micrometeorite impacts on the regolith creates small globs of glassy material (Paul *et al*, 2022). Plants were never grown in lunar regolith as the support matrix (Fertl and Paul, 2010).

Lunar samples studied on Earth contain 30–52 vol. % agglutinates, which are aggregates containing mineral fragments, nano phase metallic Fe, trapped gases, and glass that form due to micrometeorite impacts (Labotka *et al*, 1980). Natural volcanic glass does not fully replicate agglutinate assemblages or morphologies (Hill *et al*, 2007). Lunar regoliths derived from high-Ti basaltic bedrock have TiO₂ abundances of 5-7 wt. %.

In lunar rocks and soils, 99% of the mass consists of the following seven chemical elements: Oxygen (41-45 %) | Silicon (Si) | Aluminum (Al) | Calcium (Ca) | Iron (Fe) | Magnesium (Mg) | Titanium (Ti). Nearly all the remaining 1 % consists to these chemical elements: Manganese (Mn) | Sodium (Na) | Potassium (K) | Phosphorous (P).

Quartz is a form SiO₂, but quartz is rare on the Moon. On Earth, SiO₂ concentrations in rocks vary from 0% to 100%. The variation on the Moon is much less because the 3 major minerals in lunar rocks, plagioclase feldspar (usually anorthite), pyroxene, and olivine, all have about the same SiO₂ concentration.

Concentrations of Ti vary by a factor of 10 in basaltic lunar soils. Na concentrations in lunar samples are much lower than they are in most terrestrial samples. Na is an element that is often good for distinguishing between lunar and terrestrial samples. Like Na, K concentrations in lunar samples are much lower than they are in most terrestrial samples. Potassium is an element that is often good for distinguishing between lunar and terrestrial samples. Phosphorus in not particularly useful for distinguishing between lunar and terrestrial samples.

PUMICE Stone

Volcanic Ash (VA) is composed of a mixture of pumice, glass shards, rock fragments, and variable proportions of crystals or crystal fragments of various silicate minerals such s pyroxenes, feldspars, quartz, and cristobalite (Plumlee and Ziegler, 2005).

Because of the oxidizing environment, iron and manganese concentrations are very low or not detected despite the high concentrations of these elements in the host rock (Kresic and Stevanovic, 2010). Based on mineralogy there are eight types of pumice: (1) plagioclase dominant; (2) plagioclase + clinopyroxenes; (3) plagioclase + orthopyroxenes; (4) plagioclase + clinopyroxenes + orthopyroxenes; (5) plagioclase + biotite; (6) plagioclase + hornblende; (7) plagioclase + hornblende + pyroxene + quartz; and (8) plagioclase + clinopyroxenes + quartz. (Mukhopadhyay *et al*, 2003)

Pumice can have a wide variety of cations, metals, and anions that are readily leached from fresh ash, including (depending upon the volcano) Ca, Cl, SiO₂, SO₄, Mg, Na, Fe, and Mn, in 1–100 mg l⁻¹ concentrations (1:4 solid: liquid by weight), and Zn, Cd, and Pb in µg l⁻¹ concentrations. The small size of individual ash particles, however, has limited direct density measurements (Cashman and Rust, 2016).

Volcanic rocks—basalts, andesites, and their more coarsely crystalline counterparts, such as gabbro—contain minerals

that have lower concentrations of silica and higher concentrations of magnesium and iron. These are igneous minerals, formed at high temperatures, and are generally not stable in the presence of water. The igneous minerals react with groundwater, releasing alkali ions as well as Mg, Ca, and silica.

Volcanic rocks in the form of lava flows tend to be highly porous (White, 2010). Pyroclastic flows and pumice deposits are extremely permeable. Other volcanic rocks are tight, glassy, and have almost no permeability.

Pumice stone is an amorphous aluminosilicate formed by tetrahedral silica with some units being replaced by aluminate, AlO_2 . ²⁷ Al Nuclear Magnetic Resonance of pumice is indicative of tetrahedrally coordinated aluminum (Venezia *et al*, 1992).

Organic Carbon Formation in the Soil

Soil organic matter (SOM) is composed of soil microbes including bacteria and fungi, decaying material from once-living organisms such as plant and animal tissues, fecal material, and products formed from their decomposition. SOM is a heterogeneous mixture of materials that range in stage of decomposition from fresh plant residues to highly decomposed material known as humus. SOM is made of organic compounds that are highly enriched in carbon. Soil organic carbon (SOC) levels are directly related to the amount of organic matter contained in soil and SOC is often how organic matter is measured in soils.

Soil C results both directly from growth and death of plant roots, as well as indirectly from the transfer of carbon-enriched compounds from roots to soil microbes. Plants form symbiotic associations between their roots and specialized fungi in the soil known as mycorrhizae; the roots provide the fungi energy in the form of carbon while the fungi provide the plant with often-limiting nutrients such as phosphorus. Humus has a high resistance to decomposition, which in turn leads to a long residence time in soil. Plant debris is less recalcitrant, resulting in a much shorter residence time in soil.

The amount of C in soil represents a substantial portion of the carbon found in terrestrial ecosystems of the planet. Total C in terrestrial ecosystems is approximately 3170 gigatons (GT; 1 GT = 1 petagram = 1 billion metric tons). Of this amount, nearly 80% (2500 GT) is found in soil (Lal, 2004). Soil carbon can be either organic (1550 GT) or inorganic carbon (950 GT). The latter consists of elemental carbon and carbonate materials such as calcite, dolomite, and gypsum (Lal, 2008). The amount of carbon found in living plants and animals is comparatively small relative to that found in soil (560 GT). The soil carbon pool is approximately 3.1 times larger than the atmospheric pool of 800 GT (Oelkers and Cole, 2008). Oelkers & Cole (2008). Only the ocean has a larger carbon pool, at about 38,400 GT of C, mostly in inorganic forms (Houghton, 2007).

Soil texture — the relative proportions of sand, silt, and clay particles that make up a particular soil — or the mineralogy of those soil particles can have a significant impact on soil

carbon stocks. The carbon released to the atmosphere through deforestation includes carbon emitted from the decomposition of aboveground plant biomass, carbon levels in the soil are also rapidly depleted from the decomposition of SOM. The decomposition of SOM is due to the activity of the microbial decomposer community in the absence of continual rates of carbon input from the growth of forest vegetation, as well as increased soil temperatures. The rate of exchange of carbon pool between the atmosphere and the soil is estimated to be higher than that between the atmosphere and the ocean.

Increased temperatures may also lead to higher rates of SOM decomposition, which may in turn produce more CO_2 , resulting in positive feedbacks on climate change (Pataki *et al*, 2003). Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) levels result from the interactions of several ecosystem processes, of which photosynthesis, respiration, and decomposition are key. Photosynthesis is the fixation of atmospheric CO_2 into plant biomass. SOC input rates are primarily determined by the root biomass of a plant, but also include litter deposited from plant shoots.

Theoretical framework of QBLOCK™

As a result of our research work, we found several molecules in the human eye capable of transforming light energy into chemical energy by dissociating the water molecule, just like plants (Herrera *et al*, 2005). It was a study that lasted 12 years (1990-2002) and included ophthalmological records of 6000 patients. By delving into the study of the dissociation of water and its consequent effects on the metabolism of the human body, we realized that the levels of oxygen (and hydrogen) coming from the dissociation of water are critical for the development and normal functioning of the human body. And by extending our experiments to plants and soil, we found that much the same thing happens. That is: the levels of oxygen (and hydrogen) that the dissociation of water generates are essential for the soil to be fertile, since once the levels of these gases are adequate, the rest of the components of the subsoil biological system they start to appear.

That study ended in 2002, and we were able to replicate the dissociation of water in the lab in 2007, just as it happens in the human eye. From there we began to test the process for different processes, both natural and industrial, with positive results. For this reason, we are now interested in reporting our results in relation to agricultural soil fertility, especially in extreme environments, given that food production is an emergency, and our process constitutes a before and after in the thorny problem of lack of food.

Problem Statement

Soil fertility is declining all over the world, and there seems to be no solution. However, a fortuitous finding opens a new panorama: the levels of dissolved oxygen that agricultural (and non-agricultural) soil contain.

The production of meals in inhospitable areas is a problem that does not have a simple solution. And worst, soil fertility has been declining worldwide. The challenge is to

restore the ability of arable soil to produce food with minimal or no fertilizer use. According to previous experiments conducted in our laboratory, oxygen levels are critical for the fertility of arable soil and are even more important than levels of nitrogen and phosphates (Herrera *et al*, 2022), because if oxygen levels are maintained at adequate levels in the soil, then nitrogen and phosphate appears, produced naturally by the subsurface micro biome that are highly oxygen dependent. Raising artificially nitrogen or phosphate levels in the soil, for example with nitrogen or phosphate fertilizers, it will cause that oxygen levels in the subsoil to tend to decrease, since nitrogen tends to displace oxygen. Which is one of the explanations about the progressive loss of agricultural soil fertility worldwide, since the senseless use of nitrogen and phosphate fertilizers has been indiscriminate, reaching the irrationality.

With this experiment, we want to demonstrate that the elevation of oxygen levels in the subsoil, for example with QBLOCKS™, is sufficient to induce appearance of organic carbon and thereby nitrogen and phosphate compounds (Herrera, 2016) in soils so difficult to cultivate as Pumice.

The objective of this experiment was to study the effect of QBLOCKS™ in extreme conditions, such as volcanic soil (Pumice), with the purpose of transforming it into fertile soil, and then applying it for food production in harsh environments on Earth and possibly in deep space (Moon, Mars).

In previous experiments we have managed to grow in beach sand added with QBLOCKS™ (Figure 1), obtaining good results. But now, the next step is to test pumice with QBLOCKS™ and water, given their relative resemblance to lunar soil. (Figure 2)

Figure 1: Various types of soil, the fertility of which improves with QBLOCKS™, on the left, cultivation with beach sand.

Figure 2: Pumice. Appearance of the dry material used in this experiment.

Material and Methods:

In polyethylene plastic containers, QBLOCK™ was placed, followed by distilled water to cover completely our material. Immediately Pumice was applied, until there was

no liquid water left, and the surface of the pumice was observed completely moistened. Because the components of Pumice repelled water, the next day the water had separated from Pumice. (Figure 3, 4)

Figure 3: In a polyethylene container, 400 ml of distilled water were placed, and a 100 g QBLOCK™ was placed. Appearance at the beginning of the experiment.

Figure 4: During preparation of the experiment (June 2022), no liquid water was left. And Pumice was completely soaked.

During few hours, Pumice seems as expanded, but the next day, Pumice separates from water forming a clear interface liquid/solid. The supernatant water was not removed.

Only an initial sample was taken to determine the physicochemical variables that we consider relevant, and then compare them once the organic carbon could appear.

Control of the experiments was mainly photographic. No chemical determinations of organic carbon were made since the methods described are highly polluting.

QBLOCK™ is a novel material developed at our laboratory based on the biology of the human eye, which is

characterized by maintaining in good condition the oxygen and pH of the surroundings (Herrera *et al*, 2022), whether it's water, land, or the air itself. QBLOCK™ is in the process of patenting in several countries.

Figure 5: The experiment began in June 2022, and we noticed a gradual formation of spaces that appears in few weeks.

Figure 6: Over the course of four months, the appearance of gaps and bubbles increases gradually throughout the months, as well as a slight change in coloration is observed macroscopically.

Figure 7: The appearance of the pumice in this container was very uniform at the beginning of the experiment (June 2022).

Figure 8: There are numerous small areas of organic carbon formation, indicated by dots of green coloration. This photograph was taken on November 17, 2022; and corresponds to the container shown in photograph 7.

Figure 9: Detail of the photograph 8. There are several places where the small areas of formation of organic carbon, that are detected by the green coloration. And as expected, the formation of organic carbon is occurring only on the daylight lit side of the plastic container; both photographs were taken on the same day, that is, November 17, 2022.

Figure 10) Under UV light, bubbles coming from QBLOCKS™ are visible. Interesting, Pumice Stone keep floatability after 6 months submerged in water in presence of our material (bottom).

Figure 11: In the presence of QBLOCKS™, buried in Pumice sand, the buoyancy of Pumice stones, is mixed, as some float and others lose buoyancy.

Figure 12: Organic carbon increases significantly from June 2, 2022, until December 5, 2022.

Figure 13) Organic carbon (green dots) in greater detail. This magnification corresponds to the photograph of figure 12, taken on December 5, 2022.

Figure 14) Photograph taken on December 9, 2022. Once the first visual signs of the presence of organic carbon appeared, the process seemed to speed up.

Figure 15) Abundant Organic carbon (green and brown dots) Image taken on December 17, 2022. The difference between this photograph and that of figure 14 is six days, from December 9, 2022 to December 15, 2022, however, the appearance of organic carbon was almost explosive.

Figure 16: Photograph taken on December 27, 2022. The same thing happens again between this photograph of December 27, 2022, and the photograph of December 15, 2022 (Figure 15). The difference between the amount of organic carbon, denoted by the presence of green spots of different shades, as well as dark spots, and even spots of a pink tone, is very significant.

Figure 17: On January 25, 2023, an explosive hatching of compounds compatible with the presence of organic carbon can be seen.

When oxygen levels rise in agricultural soil (like very first step), the soil becomes fertile without the need for fertilizers. Oxygen is more important than phosphates and nitrogen since high oxygen levels favor the generation of phosphates and nitrogen by the rhizome that is being formed naturally, as it has been since the beginning of time.

Results:

After five months (June -November 2022), there are not significant changes, except by the formation of relatively small empty spaces inside the pumice sand, probably due to the activity of QBLOCK™. Five months later, on November 17, 2022; it was observed by first time the presence of organic carbon denoted by small green dots, detected in the photographic control of the experiment.

From November 17 to January 25,2023, it was a significant burst of green dots. It is interesting the fragmentation of the interface between pumice sand and water, especially adjoin to organic carbon which means the growing of the green organism to the surface, possibly an alga of some type, that was not visible at the publication of this work.

Comment

Soil carbon storage is a vital ecosystem service, resulting from interactions of ecological processes. Human activities affecting these processes had led to carbon loss, which is responsible of the loss of soil fertility.

After several years of study about the dynamic of the oxygen through living things and environment (atmosphere, water, and soil) we understood the huge importance of the oxygen levels. The interplay between the different living things and the surroundings with the molecular Oxygen is relatively accurate. This mean that with adequate oxygen levels, life hatch and express fruitful. Oppositely, when Oxygen levels decrease, and this by several reasons -water pollution, pesticides, herbicides, fertilizers, industrial waste, etc. -; the other components are significantly affected and their capacity to sustain some form of life is reduced significantly.

The appearance of organic carbon means that at least, some terrestrial plants are capable of growth in Pumice sand as the primary support matrix in presence of high levels of oxygen. Pumice sand is a harsh environment for plant growth, alike lunar regolith that also is not a benign growth substrate.

Conclusion

Soil organic matter is the largest terrestrial carbon pool (Schlesinger and Bernhardt, 2013). The pool size depends on the balance between formation of soil organic matter from decomposition of plant litter and its mineralization to inorganic carbon. Knowledge of soil organic matter formation remains limited (Schmidt *et al*, 2011). It is assumed that stable soil organic matter is formed primarily from recalcitrant plant litter (Smith *et al*, 1997).

Organic matter is a key component of soil that affects its physical, chemical, and biological properties, contributing

greatly to its proper functioning. Soil quality through increased retention of water and nutrients, resulting in greater productivity of plants in natural environments and agricultural settings.

We don't have a very good analog for lunar or Mars soil, and we don't have enough regolith samples to make these sorts of experiments possible. Working on materials that could enable these kinds of studies is the most pressing need going forward.

However, results like this allows a reasonable optimism about food production in harsh terrestrial environments and highly possible in deep space, based on the unraveling importance of dissolved oxygen that soil contains, and not in phosphates and nitrogen.

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